

SCHOOL CLIMATE AND ORGANIZATIONAL LEARNING CAPABILITIES AMONG TEACHERS IN POLANCO DISTRICT II, Zamboanga, del Norte

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research was to assess the school climate and organizational learning capacity of teachers in the Polanco II District during 2020. To achieve this, a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design was employed. A total of 154 instructors in the Polanco II District participated in the study, and data was collected using various statistical tools, including frequency counting and percent, weighted mean, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation.

The results of the study showed that the perceived school climate in the district was very high. All indicators had standard deviations below 3.00, suggesting that the mean responses were closely grouped together. The organizational learning capability of the district was assessed to be fairly strong. The data revealed that the teachers' perceptions of school climate and organizational learning capability were highly correlated and significantly associated with organizational learning capability.

In summary, this study provides evidence that the Polanco II District has a positive school climate and strong organizational learning capability. These findings may be useful in identifying areas for improvement and developing interventions to further enhance the district's educational environment.

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Introduction

The pandemic has led to a paradigm shift in education (Thuli, Vilhelmson, & Johansson, 2019, Sarif, 2020), emphasizing the importance of organizational learning capacities, flexibility, and adaptability to ensure the best learning outcomes and protect the well-being of teachers and students (Darvasi, 2020, Lyman et al., 2020, Robosa, et al., 2021). School atmosphere indirectly impacts instructors' education abilities, and school support for teachers and students has a significant direct impact on organizational learning capacities (Louis & Murphy, 2017; Jaafari et al., 2017; Maxwell et al., 2017). However, there is a lack of research on the inefficient distribution of educational resources and learning materials in some areas (Polanco II District, Zamboanga del Norte, Division, Region IX,

Department of Education), highlighting the need for constructive social development through communication between educators and school managers. Flaherty (2020) noted the debate among academics on social media about the impact of solitude on research productivity, emphasizing the importance of a positive learning environment and school climate in promoting employee output and performance (Alawamleh, Al-Twait, & Al-Saht, 2020).

In summary, the COVID-19 pandemic has had significant implications for education, highlighting the importance of organizational learning capacities, flexibility, and adaptability in ensuring the best learning outcomes and protecting the well-being of teachers and students. The school atmosphere and support for teachers and students play crucial roles in shaping the learning environment, and innovative measures such as virtual learning environments and flexible teaching methods have enabled institutions to maintain learning continuity while prioritizing safety and well-being. This study could be an answer to the need for more research work in this area to promote constructive social development. This determined the school climate and organizational learning capabilities among teachers in Polanco District II.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the school climate and organizational learning capabilities among teachers in Polanco II District during the school year 2020-2021.

Specifically, the research sought answers to the following questions:

- 1. What is the profile of the teachers in terms of**
 - 1.1 sex;*
 - 1.2 age;*
 - 1.3 educational attainment;*
 - 1.4 years in service; and*
 - 1.5 designation (T1, T2, MT1, MT2)?*
- 2. What is the level of school climate in Polanco II District during the COVID-19 pandemic in terms of**
 - 2.1 collaboration;*
 - 2.2 student relations;*
 - 2.3 school resources;*
 - 2.4 decision making; and*
 - 2.5 instructional innovation?*
- 3. Is there a significant difference in the perceived level of school climate when data are analyzed according to profile?**
- 4. What is the level of organizational learning capabilities in Polanco II District COVID-19 pandemic in terms of**
 - 4.1 experimentation;*
 - 4.2 risk-taking;*

4.3 interaction with the external environment;

4.4 dialogue; and

4.5 participative in decision-making?

5. Is there a significant difference in the perceived level of organizational learning capabilities when data are analyzed according to profile?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the perceived level of school climate and organizational learning capabilities?

Methodology

Method Used

The study utilized a combination of survey and correlational research methods to examine the relationship between organizational learning capacity and school climate. A survey approach was employed to collect information from a predetermined set of respondents using a questionnaire checklist. According to Creswell and Guetterman (2019), a survey is an effective research technique for obtaining new perspectives and insights on various topics. On the other hand, correlational research is a non-experimental methodology that examines the statistical relationship between two variables, without the interference of any additional variables (Bhat, 2019). The researchers conducted a correlational analysis to determine the extent of the relationship between the variables, as well as the respondents' profile and their level of subject understanding.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Polanco District, which is a school district located in the Zamboanga del Norte province of the Philippines. The municipality is situated 15 kilometers to the east of Dipolog City and comprises of 14 elementary and three secondary schools. Based on the division's Personal Services Itemization and Plantilla of Personnel, the elementary level has 108 teaching personnel, while the second level has 46 teaching personnel.

Respondents of the Study

Respondents included 14 elementary schools and three secondary schools in the Polanco II District of the Division of Zamboanga del Norte. The distribution of instructors in the 14 elementary schools and three secondary schools is shown in Table 1.

Distribution of Respondents' Schools

Table 1

School	Population/Respondents	Percent
1. Bethlehem ES	9	5.19
2. Dangi ES	6	3.90
3. Dansullan ES	7	4.55
4. De Venta Perla ES	7	4.55
5. Lapayanbaja ES	8	5.19
6. Linabo ES	1	0.65
7. Macleodes ES	7	4.55
8. Maligaya PS	4	2.60
9. Milad ES	8	5.19
10. New Libangon ES	6	3.90
11. New Sicayab ES	10	6.49
12. San Pedro ES	8	5.19
13. Sianib ES	7	4.55
14. Silawe CS	20	12.99
15. San Pedro NHS	21	13.64
16. Sianib NHS	9	5.84
17. Silawe NHS	16	10.39
Total	154	100.00

As of November 24, 2021

Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in the study consisted of three sections: the respondent profile, the school climate scale, and the organizational learning capability scale. The respondent profile section collected information about the respondent's gender, age, and highest educational qualification. To measure the school climate, Johnson, Stevens,

and Zvoch (2007) developed a school environment measure that included dimensions such as cooperation, student relationships, school resources, decision-making, and instructional innovation.

For measuring organizational learning capability, Chiva and Alegre's (2009) scale was used, which included dimensions such as experimentation, risk-taking, interaction with the external environment, dialogue, and participatory decision-making. The instruments were reviewed by a panel of experts, including external experts and the graduate school dean as chairperson, to ensure content validity. Feedback from the experts was integrated into the final version of the questionnaire. Additionally, the instruments were subjected to pilot testing to assess their reliability.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument underwent a review by the research advisor and four experts, and their feedback was incorporated into the final draft. To evaluate its reliability, a pilot test was conducted with a sample of 43 individuals who shared similar characteristics with the study participants. The instrument's internal consistency was measured using Cronbach's Alpha, which was interpreted using a guide provided by Tox (2020). The results showed that the school climate scale received an excellent Cronbach Alpha score of 0.88 for its 20 items, while the organizational learning capability scale received an outstanding Cronbach Alpha value of 0.93 for its 13 components. Additionally, the internal consistency reliability of both instruments was determined to be outstanding.

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Internal Consistency</i>
<i>0.90 & above</i>	<i>Excellent</i>
<i>0.80 – 0.89</i>	<i>Good</i>
<i>0.70 – 0.79</i>	<i>Acceptable</i>
<i>0.60 – 0.69</i>	<i>Questionable</i>
<i>0.50 – 0.59</i>	<i>Poor</i>
<i>Below 0.50</i>	<i>Unacceptable</i>

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Presented below were the statistical tools utilized in the treatment and analysis of the data gathered.

Frequency Counting and Percent. They were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, and educational attainment.

Weighted Mean. This was used to quantify the respondents' ratings on the school climate and organizational learning capability.

The following is a scoring guide for providing a qualitative description and interpretation of the responses to the items in the school climate and organizational learning capability scales:

School Climate

Scale	Range of Measures	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Almost Always	Very much observed
4	3.41-4.20	More Often	Much Observed
3	2.61-3.40	Often	Observed
2	1.81-2.60	Sometimes	Slightly Observed
1	1.00-1.80	Never	Not Observed

Organizational Learning Capability

Scale	Range of Measures,	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Almost Always	Very Much Capable
4	3.41-4.20	More Often	Much Capable
3	2.61-3.40	Often	Capable
2	1.81-2.60	Sometimes	Slightly Capable
1	1.00-1.80	Never	Not Capable

Standard Deviation This was used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the students’ scores where SD ≤ 3 is homogenous and SD > 3 is heterogeneous (Aiken & Susane, 2001; Refugio, Galleto, & Torres, 2019).

Mann-Whitney U Test. This was used to test the difference in organizational learning capability and work engagement when respondents are grouped in terms of sex.

Kruskal-Wallis Test. This was used to test the difference in organizational learning capability and work engagement when respondents are grouped in terms of age, year of experience, position, and educational attainment.

Spearman Rank-Order Correlation. This was used to determine the correlation between school climate and organizational learning capability.

The following guide in interpreting the correlation value suggested by Cohen, West, and Aiken (2014) was utilized in this study:

<i>Value</i>	<i>Size</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>±0.50 to ±1.00</i>	<i>Large</i>	<i>High positive/negative correlation</i>
<i>±0.30 to ±0.49</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Moderate positive/negative correlation</i>
<i>±0.10 to ±0.29</i>	<i>Small</i>	<i>Low positive/negative correlation</i>
<i>±0.01 to ±0.09</i>	<i>Negligible</i>	<i>Slight positive/negative correlation</i>
<i>0.00</i>		<i>No correlation</i>

Results And Discussion

Perceived Level of School Climate

Table 2

School Climate	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Collaboration	4.51	0.55	Almost Always	Very Much Observed
B. Student Relation	4.12	0.59	More Often	Much Observed
C. School Resources	3.95	0.82	More Often	Much Observed
D. Decision Making	4.15	0.73	More Often	Much Observed
E. Instructional Innovation	4.44	0.58	Almost Always	Very Much Observed
Overall Mean	4.27	0.69	Almost Always	Very Much Observed

Table 2 summarizes the perceived level of school climate. Respondents rated collaboration as the highest (mean=4.51, SD=0.55) and instructional innovation as the second highest (mean=4.44, SD=0.58), both interpreted as “very much observed.” Student relations, school resources, and decision-making were described as “much observed.” On average, respondents indicated a “very much observed” (mean=4.27, SD=0.69) school climate in Polanco II District, indicating a good implementation of the Distance Learning Delivery Modality (DLDM). This supports Marcotte's (2021) findings that a good school climate motivates teachers to improve student achievement.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of School Climate in terms of Sex

Table 3

School Climate	U-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Collaboration	905.000	0.066	Not Significant
B. Student Relation	1,082.000	0.389	Not Significant
C. School Resources	1,036.500	0.286	Not Significant
D. Decision Making	1,091.500	0.439	Not Significant
E. Instructional Innovation	1,154.500	0.689	Not Significant
Overall	1,010.000	0.228	Not Significant

Table 3 displays the Mann-Whitney U test results for the perceived level of school climate by sex. The test revealed no significant difference in how male and female respondents perceive school climate (U=1,010.00, p=0.228). Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating that sex does not significantly affect the perception of school

climate. However, this finding contradicts Misnawati's (2020) study, which found that school climate significantly impacted both male and female teachers.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of School Climate in terms of Age

Table 4

School Climate	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Collaboration	2.351	0.503	Not Significant
B. Student Relation	4.436	0.218	Not Significant
C. School Resources	5.952	0.114	Not Significant
D. Decision Making	10.273	0.016	Significant
E. Instructional Innovation	1.276	0.735	Not Significant
Overall	3.787	0.285	Not Significant

Table 4 displays the variation in perceived school climate by age using the Kruskal-Wallis H test. Results indicate a significant difference in decision-making (H=10.273, p=0.016), but no significant difference for collaboration, student relations, school resources, and instructional innovation. The null hypothesis is not rejected for the overall perceived school climate (H=3.787, p=0.285), implying that age does not significantly impact respondents' perceptions. Marcotte (2021) supports this observation, stating that age has no bearing on the school climate during remote teaching.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of School Climate in terms of Educational Attainment

Table 5

School Climate	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Collaboration	0.906	0.924	Not Significant
B. Student Relation	3.564	0.468	Not Significant
C. School Resources	5.327	0.255	Not Significant
D. Decision Making	5.508	0.239	Not Significant
E. Instructional Innovation	9.035	0.060	Not Significant
Overall	3.739	0.442	Not Significant

Table 5, using the Kruskal-Wallis H test, shows no significant difference in the perceived level of school climate by educational attainment (H=3.739, p=0.442). As a result, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This means that respondents' perception of school climate does not vary significantly based on their educational level. This finding is different from Marcotte's (2021) study, which found that educational attainment affects the effectiveness of teaching strategies and impacts school organization performance.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of School Climate in terms of Years of Experience

Table 6

School Climate	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Collaboration	3.367	0.338	Not Significant
B. Student Relation	7.833	0.050	Significant
C. School Resources	7.705	0.053	Not Significant
D. Decision Making	13.912	0.003	Significant
E. Instructional Innovation	4.290	0.232	Not Significant
Overall	8.017	0.046	Significant

Table 6 presents the Kruskal-Wallis H test to determine the difference in the perceived level of school climate when respondents are categorized according to years of experience. The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the school climate for collaboration, school resources, and instructional innovation. However, there is a significant difference in school climate concerning student relations and decision-making. The aggregate result also shows a significant difference in school climate (H=8.017, p=0.046) when respondents are categorized by years of experience. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that individuals with more experience perceive school climate differently. Post hoc analysis using pairwise comparison with Bonferroni correction identified the specific differences in student relationships and decision-making across different age groups. This finding contradicts Misnawati's (2020) study, which proposed that the school environment should be considered in enhancing student participation and strengthening their connections, and the effect of the school environment is mediated by year level of experience.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of School Climate in terms of Position

Table 7

School Climate	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Collaboration	4.784	0.310	Not Significant
B. Student Relation	2.310	0.679	Not Significant
C. School Resources	6.998	0.136	Not Significant
D. Decision Making	12.687	0.013	Significant
E. Instructional Innovation	2.008	0.734	Not Significant
Overall	5.417	0.247	Not Significant

Table 7 shows the Kruskal-Wallis H test of difference in the perceived level of school atmosphere when respondents are grouped by rank. There is a significant variation in the perceived degree of school atmosphere for decision-making, but no significant difference in the reported school climate regarding collaboration, student relations, school

resources, and instructional innovation. The null hypothesis is not rejected when respondents are classified by rank, indicating that respondents' perceptions of school climate in different teaching positions are not significantly different ($H=5.417$, $p=0.247$). This finding contradicts Marcotte's (2021) study, which found a statistically significant difference in the school environment and gender, teaching experience, and teaching position during remote instruction.

Perceived Level of Organizational Learning Capability in terms of Experimentation

Table 8

Experimentation	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Teachers receive support and encouragement when presenting new ideas	4.30	0.54	Almost Always	Very Much Capable
2. Teachers' initiative often receives a favorable response here so; they feel encouraged to generate new ideas	4.27	0.54	Almost Always	Very Much Capable
Overall Mean	4.28	0.54	Almost Always	Very Much Capable

The table shows high perceived organizational learning capabilities in experimentation (mean=4.28, SD=0.54). Respondents considered the Polanco II District schools "very much capable" in this area and initiatives were well-received. School administrators and instructors are skilled in presenting new concepts and receiving support for them. This is consistent with Heniel and Naparota's (2021) findings that staff members received support and encouragement for new ideas and could come up with original ones.

Perceived Level of Organizational Learning Capability

Table 9

Organizational Learning Capability	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Experimentation	4.28	0.54	Almost Always	Very Much Capable
B. Risk Taking	4.19	0.61	More Often	Much Capable
C. Interaction with the External Environment	4.33	0.57	Almost Always	Very Much Capable
D. Dialogue	4.52	0.55	Almost Always	Very Much Capable
E. Participative Decision Making	4.34	0.60	Almost Always	Very Much Capable
Overall Mean	4.36	0.58	Almost Always	Very Much Capable

Table 9 summarizes respondents' perceived level of organizational learning capability, showing that Polanco II District schools are "extremely capable" in experimentation, engagement with the external environment, dialogue, participatory decision-making, and "quite capable" in risk-taking. Overall, organizational learning competence in these schools is considered "highly capable" (mean=4.36, SD=0.58). This finding suggests that the Learning Delivery Modality (LDM 1 & 2) course has been effective. Heniel and Naparota (2021) reported on Chiva and Alegre's (2009) study, which demonstrated the value of Organizational Learning Capability dimensions for measuring an organization's performance and ability to innovate and expand. There is also evidence of a positive relationship between employee attitudes and Organizational Learning Capabilities.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of Organizational Learning Capability in Terms of Sex

Table 10

Organizational Learning Capability	U-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Experimentation	1,027.500	0.222	Not Significant
B. Risk Taking	987.000	0.148	Not Significant
C. Interaction with the External Environment	1,021.500	0.231	Not Significant
D. Dialogue	1,078.500	0.394	Not Significant
E. Participative Decision Making	1,035.000	0.238	Not Significant
Overall	1,018.00	0.244	Not Significant

Table 10 encapsulates that Polanco II District schools are "extremely capable" in experimentation, engagement with the external environment, dialogue, and participatory decision-making, while risk-taking is "quite capable." Overall, the organizational learning competence in these schools is considered "highly capable" (mean=4.36, SD=0.58). This finding suggests that the Learning Delivery Modality (LDM 1 & 2) course has been effective. Heniel and Naparota (2021) reported on Chiva and Alegre's (2009) study, which recognized Organizational Learning Capability dimensions as a critical measure of an organization's performance and innovation. The characteristics of Organizational Learning Capability are believed to benefit both organizations and employees, with empirical evidence supporting a positive relationship between employee attitudes and Organizational Learning Capabilities.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of Organizational Learning Capability in terms of Age

Table 11

Organizational Learning Capability	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Experimentation	9.276	0.026	Significant
B. Risk Taking	0.872	0.832	Not Significant
C. Interaction with External Environment	4.090	0.252	Not Significant
D. Dialogue	5.777	0.123	Not Significant

E. Participative Decision Making	6.079	0.108	Not Significant
Overall	5.384	0.146	Not Significant

Table 11, analyzed with the Kruskal-Wallis H test, indicates a significant difference in perceived organizational learning capability in terms of experimentation among respondents of different age groups. However, there is no significant difference in organizational learning capability regarding risk-taking, engagement with the external environment, dialogue, and participatory decision-making. The test results ($H=5.384$, $p=0.146$) show that there is no significant difference in organizational learning capability across age groups, thus failing to reject the null hypothesis. This finding aligns with Heniel and Naparota's (2021) study, which found no significant difference in Organizational Learning Capability among respondents grouped by age. Age is not a reliable factor for identifying differences in Organizational Learning Capability, and respondents' levels of Organizational Learning Capability do not significantly differ based on age classification.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of Organizational Learning Capability in terms of Educational Attainment

Table 12

Organizational Learning Capability	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Experimentation	1.843	0.765	Not Significant
B. Risk Taking	1.918	0.751	Not Significant
C. Interaction with External Environment	0.694	0.952	Not Significant
D. Dialogue	2.912	0.573	Not Significant
E. Participative Decision-Making	7.604	0.107	Not Significant
Overall	2.789	0.594	Not Significant

The Kruskal-Wallis H test shows no significant difference in perceived organizational learning capability based on educational attainment ($H=2.789$, $p=0.594$), and the null hypothesis is not rejected. Heniel and Naparota (2021) agree with these findings, noting no significant variation or predictability based on educational attainment.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of Organizational Learning Capability in terms of Years in Service

Table 13

Organizational Learning Capability	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Experimentation	10.319	0.016	Significant
B. Risk Taking	10.505	0.037	Significant
C. Interaction with External Environment	12.077	0.007	Significant
D. Dialogue	8.699	0.034	Significant
E. Participative Decision Making	12.742	0.005	Significant
Overall	13.154	0.004	Significant

Table 13, using the Kruskal-Wallis H test, indicates a significant difference in perceived organizational learning capability by years of service ($H=13.154$, $p=0.004$), rejecting the null hypothesis. Post hoc analysis, employing the Mann-Whitney U test with Bonferroni correction, showed specific service years with significant differences in experimentation, risk-taking, interaction with the external environment, risk-taking, dialogue, and participative decision-making. Age ranges with significant differences were 6-10 years and 16 years and older, and 11-15 years and 16 years and older. These results differ from Deniz, Cimen, and Kaya's (2017) study which found no significant variation based on employee tenure.

Test of Difference in the Perceived Level of Organizational Learning Capability in Terms of Position

Table 14

Organizational Learning Capability	H-value	p-value @ 0.05	Interpretation
A. Experimentation	11.975	0.019	Significant
B. Risk Taking	0.819	0.936	Not Significant
C. Interaction with External Environment	6.812	0.146	Not Significant
D. Dialogue	6.199	0.185	Not Significant
E. Participative Decision-Making	10.314	0.035	Significant
Overall	7.126	0.126	Not Significant

Table 14, using Kruskal-Wallis H test, shows significant contrasts in experimental and participatory decision-making, but no essential variations in risk-taking, interaction with the outside world, or discourse when respondents are classified by rank. However, when respondents are classified by position, there is no significant difference in perceived organizational learning capability ($H=7.126$, $p=0.126$), and the null hypothesis is not rejected, indicating no considerable differences in respondents' responses across different positions. Deniz, Cimen, and Kaya (2017) also found no substantial variation in organizational learning capacity based on job positions.

Test of Relationship between School Climate and Organizational Learning Capability

Table 15

Variables	ρ -value	p-value	Interpretation
School Climate			
vs	0.803	< 0.001	High Positive Correlation/Significant
Organizational Learning Capability			

In Table 15, Spearman Rank-Order Correlation (Spearman rho) is used to examine the association between school atmosphere and organizational learning capability. The results show a highly positive association (ρ -value=0.803, p-value 0.001) between teachers' reported school climate and organizational learning capability, indicating that the perceived quality of school climate affects teachers' organizational learning capabilities positively. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that as the school climate's perceived level rises, so will organizational learning capability, suggesting that the school climate influences organizational learning capabilities. The study contradicts Ramirez's (2020) research, which found no significant association between school atmosphere and organizational learning skills, nor did it reveal a significant difference when grouped based on individual characteristics.

Conclusions

The study found that elementary school teachers in Polanco, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines, exhibit maturity, but only a minority of them place importance on pursuing graduate studies. They prioritize collaboration, instructional innovation, maintaining student interactions, and fostering a positive school atmosphere when using the Distance Learning Delivery Modality (DLDM). While teachers' positions and educational attainment did not correspond to the level of school atmosphere, the research highlighted the positive influence of the Learning Delivery Modality training on teachers' organizational learning capability. Overall, teachers were found to be "very much capable" of organizational learning capability (LDM 1 & 2), and there was a significant positive association between school climate and teachers' learning abilities.

Recommendations

After analyzing the findings and conclusions of the study, several recommendations are offered to enhance the learning capabilities and learning modalities of elementary school teachers and students during the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Firstly, the study suggests that enhancing the management practices of the Department of Education (DepEd) top-level management could create a more conducive environment for learning in school classrooms. Additionally, conducting evaluations of School Heads may help ensure the maintenance of the school's learning capabilities and modalities.

Secondly, the study recommends that the School Heads of Polanco II District continue their current managerial practices in dealing with the school environment and students' relationships. This could help sustain the learning capabilities, learning modalities, students' achievement, community relationships, and safety among students.

Thirdly, the stakeholders can assist Polanco II District in enhancing the school facilities, learning capabilities, and learning modalities among teachers and students.

Fourthly, educational institutions offering Master of Arts in Educational Management and other related courses have the option to use the findings of this study as a point of reference to potentially improve school climate and learning capabilities among teachers and students, as well as learning modalities, in times of the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Lastly, future researchers may use the findings of this study as a benchmark for their research implementation to gain insights into how to further enhance the learning capabilities and learning modalities of teachers and students in elementary schools.

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